

SCOPE OF AYURVEDA IN PUBLIC HEALTH**Vaidya Shashi Tiwari¹, Dr. Neha Singh², Dr. Rishabh Jain³**¹P. G. Scholar, Second Year, Samhita Evam Siddhant Dept. - Quadra Institute of Ayurveda Roorkee.²Asst. Prof. Samhita Evam Siddhant Dept. - Quadra Institute of Ayurveda Roorkee.³HOD. Prof. Samhita Evam Siddhant Dept. - Quadra Institute of Ayurveda Roorkee.***Corresponding Author: Vaidya Shashi Tiwari**

P. G. Scholar, Second Year, Samhita Evam Siddhant Dept. - Quadra Institute of Ayurveda Roorkee.

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ABSTRACT

Ayush is an abbreviation which comprises of 5 paths in it. A stands for *Ayurveda*, Y stands for Yoga and Naturopathy, U stands for *Unani*, S stands for *Siddha* and H for Homeopathy. *Ayurveda* is a holistic science which talks about physical, mental, social and spiritual health of individual or public. *Ayurveda* is science (veda) of life (*Ayur*). *Ayurveda* focuses on both remaining healthy and disease-free life of public. For this goal it concentrates on daily routine (*Dinacharya*) and Seasonal routine (*Ritucharya*). *Dinacharya* and *Ritucharya* is a Unique concept in *Ayurveda*. It talks about both diet and lifestyle. *Aahaara* (food), *Vihaara* (activities) and *Vichaara* (thought process) is fundamental key of health in *Ayurveda*. There is proper guideline of *Aahaara* regarding its quality and quantity for each and every individual of society. *Vihaara* (actions) - which actions or behaviour should be performed by an individual for healthy body. *Vichaara* is thought Process. A person's health is affected by whatever he or she may consume in form of whether diet (*Aahaara*), actions (*Vihaara*) and *Vichaara* i.e. thought process. *Ayurveda* second goal is disease-free society. For this purpose there is a unique concept of removal of cause (*Nidan Parivarjan*). There is proper protocol of treatment of each and every disease whether named or not named because in it there is focus on doshas like disbalance of *vaat-pitta-kapha*.

KEYWORDS: Ayush, *Ayurveda*, Public health, *Aahaara*, *Vihaara*, *Vichaara*.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda has proper clear-cut concept for daily routine (*Dinacharya*) which should be followed by an individual to remain healthy and lead a disease-free life. These are as follows.

1. Wake up early in the morning before sunrise specially in early morning (e).

By this proper evacuation of natural urges like stool and urine will take place at proper time and digestive fire will be ok so that no *Aama* (toxic material) is generated in body.

Nowadays people sleep late at night (*Ratri jagaran - Vaat and Pitta Prakopa*) and wake up late in morning (*Divashayan- Kapha Prakopa*) specially after sunrise, by this their all 3 doshas are disturbed and causes many diseases.

2. After evacuation of stool and urine a person should wash their face and mouth, brushing of teeth and cleaning of tongue so that toxin is removed from mouth and feeling of freshness and foul smell is removed. By this diseases of mouth can be avoided and cured too.

3. A person should bow his head to God and elderly person in house daily for blessing. By blessing all work can occur in peaceful way and person becomes stress free. By this many mental issues can be avoided.

4. Use daily *Anjana* (medicated *Kajal*) in eyes for healthy eyes. By this dirt is removed from eyes and many eye diseases can be avoided and cured too.

5. Another step towards health is to take daily *Nasya* (pouring medicated oil, ghee, herbal juice / *Swaras* in each nostril) *Gandusha* and *Kavala* (gargling with medicated oil or herbs decoction) and *Dhoomapaana* (taking medicated smoke by nostril and expel from

mouth). By this ENT diseases ie ear, nose and throat problems can avoided and cure too.

6. A person should wear neat and clean cloth daily according to season. By this their body is protected from seasonal changes and a good dressing sense gives good looking, confidence and self-respect too.

7. A person should take *Tamboola* leaves (Beetle leaves) daily. it acts like cardiac tonic and increases haemoglobin level in body too.

8. Do some work for livelihood. Choose profession wisely and passionately so that no more stress in life and by this financial and many mental issue can avoid.

9. Say bye before going outside of house. By this person aware the other person and becomes self-responsible too. It is included in good conduct too.

10. Do *Abhyangama* (body massage with oil/medicated oil) daily in night specially Monday, Wednesday and Saturday. By this good muscle tone, lustre and glowing skin achieved and many *vaataj* diseases like pain, Numbness low blood circulation and many more issues can resolve.

11. Do exercise daily. It increases working strength, physical and mental power of body, increases digestive fire of body and helps in losing weight and help in attain good physique and overall shape the personality.

12. Apply *Uddhavartan* (rubbing of herbal powder) before bathing to all over body. It increases the blood circulation of body and removes dirt from all body parts and gives good glowing and happy skin.

13. Take proper meal after proper evacuation of natural urges and bathing. It should be according to body need.

There is a proper guideline regarding *Aahaara* in *Ayurveda* like *Ashta Aahaara vidhi Visheshayatan* (8 parameter of diet) and *Aahaara Vidhi Vidhan* (how should consume the food) in classics. They are –

1. *Prakriti* (Nature of food) - whether the food item is *Guru* (heavy to digest) or *Laghu* (light to digest). example *Moong Dal* (green gram lentils) is *Laghu* and *Urad Dal* (black gram lentils) is *Guru*.

2. *Karan* (Preparation methods) - How food is prepared also affect digestion. It included washing methods like before cooking washing of vegetables, rice and pulses in proper manner for removal of dirt and other things, type of pot using for cooking also affect digestion. Nowadays again some people started cooking in earthen pot to avoid diabetes and other disease too. Curd causes inflammation but *Takra* (by churning or *Manthan* procedure) vanishes inflammation. Drinking water in silver glass gives cool and calm mind by lowering down aggression etc. It also included time,

place and mood of individual during cooking so digestion.

3. *Sanyoga* (Combination) - Combination of certain food item together can cause serious health issues like honey and ghee in equal quantity and in warm state together, fish (specially *Chilachima* fish) and milk together, meat with honey or jaggery or *Til* (sesame) or milk or curd or radish or sprouts, sour things with milk (nowadays people are found off milkshakes specially of citrous fruits ie sour fruits), milk taken with radish causes skin diseases. These are few examples from classics. There is a separate chapter on Incompatible food combinations in our classics.

4. *Matra* (Quantity) - It is the amount of meal which a person should consume. It depends on nature of working of a person and also on digestive fire of person. Generally it should be one third solid part, one third liquid part and one third for gases of *Kukshi* (stomach). Excess amount of food is cause of all diseases and less amount of food is cause of *Vaataja* diseases.

5. *Desha* (Habitat) - A person should consume those food items or herbs which grow in his /her own habitat. Seasonal and regional fruits and vegetables suits a person in healthy manner. Nowadays people consume foreign fruits and vegetable in flow of western culture like kiwi, avocado, dragon fruits and many more. This is not advisable for good health.

6. *Kaala* (Time) - One should take food according to season, age and condition of any disease or health. After proper digestion of previous food, a person can take next meal. For example, milk is harmful in acute fever but it is beneficial in chronic fever, buffalo milk is not good generally but it is useful in case of insomnia, curd is not advisable to take daily but in period disorder it is recommended.

7. *Upayoga Sanstha* (Direction of use) - It is how, when, how much and in which condition one should take a meal.

8. *Upayokta* (User) - Who consume or eat the food is known as *Upayokta* or user. What is good and suitable for own health, one should eat only those food varieties.

Another parameter for healthy fooding (*Aahaara*) is *Aahaara Vidhi Vidhan* - It is the way how and in which situation a person is consuming its own meal. There are following Points.

A. *Ushnamashneeyat* - For good digestion one should eat food in warm condition. It gives good taste and increase digestive fire and stimulate proper secretion of digestive juices for digestion process. Nowadays people eat food stored food in fridges, canned and packed food. All the nutrient present in food destroy after some time. So, such type of food only causes sickness and not

suitable for health. After 3 hours of food preparation it becomes stale according to *Ayurveda* classics.

B. *Snigdamashneeyat* - By proper amount of oil and ghee food become tasty. It increases digestive fire and digest easily. *Anuloman* (proper evacuation of *Doshas*) of *Vaat doshas* takes place. It strengthens the body and organs and senses too. it increases fair complexion, removes dryness and smoothen the body.

C. *Matravadashneeyat* - Eating in proper amount is *Matravadashneeyat*. It balances all the doshas and increase lifespan.

D. *Jirnesheeyat* - If before digestion of previous meal, one takes another meal then it disbalances all *Doshas* and person become sick.

E. *Veeryaaviruddhamshneeyat* - Don't take opposite *Veerya* (hot and cold by nature) combination food altogether. for example, milk and fish taking at one time causes skin diseases.

F. *Eshtedeshe eshtasarvopakaranam Chashneeyat* - One should take meal in proper place and with all the desired food items. By this no psychosomatic disease will occur.

G. *Naatidrutamashneeyat* - by taking food in hurry, food particle can go in nostrils and causes depression and also proper placing in stomach is affected.

H. *Naativilambitamshneeyat* - By excess time taken during eating dissatisfaction and indigestion occur.

I. *Tanmanabhunjeeta* - No talking, no laughing is advisable during eating. One should concentrate only on eating at that moment, if not concentrated on food, then hurry issues of eating occur.

J. *Aatmanamabhisameekshya* - This diet is good or not good for me, always check before consumption.

There is also a list of food items which one can take daily and food items which cannot take daily. These are as follows-

1. Daily usable food Items
 - *Shaali* and *Shashtic* rice (Rice variety)
 - *Moong Dal* (Green gram lentils)
 - Rock salt
 - *Amla* (Indian Goose berry)
 - *Yava* (Barley)
 - *Antariksha Jal* (Space water)
 - Milk
 - Ghee
 - *Jangala* Meat
 - Honey
 - *Patola* (pointed gourd)
 - Pomegranate

- Grapes
- Sugar
- *Haritaki*
- Wheat
- *Trifala*

2. Not daily usable items –
 - *Kurchika* (milk derivative)
 - *Kilaat* (milk derivative)
 - Beef
 - Pork
 - Carabeef (buffalo meat)
 - Fish
 - Curd
 - *Urad dal* (black gram lentils)
 - And oats

3. Naturally healthy food items - Red *Shaali* Rice
 - *Moong dal* (green gram lentils)
 - *Antariksha jal* (Space water)
 - Rock salt
 - *Jivanti* Herb
 - Cow milk
 - Cow ghee
 - *Til Tel* (sesame oil)
 - Ginger
 - Grapes

4. Naturally unhealthy food items – oats
 - *Urad dal* (black gram lentils)
 - Rain water
 - *Ooshar* salt (variety of salt)
 - Mustard herb
 - Beef
 - *Chialchim* fish (fish variety)
 - Sheep ghee and milk
 - Potato

There is also a proper night regimen or routine in *Ayurveda*. Before going to bed, it is advisable to be free from all worries and prayer to God so that sound sleep will occur. Richness of sleep or sound sleep decide the richness of health of an individual.

After *Aahaara* there is another parameter i.e. *Vihaara* in which activities or actions performed by an individual is included. In *Ayurveda* another unique concept is *Vegadharan* (Holding of urges). This means by holding of natural urges all disease can occur in body. So, for healthy body one should do not hold natural physical urges and should hold mental urges. Natural non-holding urges are 13 /14 in number depends on *Acharyas* like urine, stool, semen. farting, vomiting, sneezing, belching, yawning, thrust, hunger, tear, sleep, exertional breathlessness. Natural suppressible urges are work beyond power and any bad work by body, mind and soul. There are some examples, of holding a natural urge and impairment in body issues. For example, holding of urine

is the major cause of all type of menstrual problems in ladies. So aware the females not to hold urine urges. Holding of stool can cause calf muscle pain, headache and gas formation. Holding of vomiting urge causes skin disease. Sense organs become weak by holding sneezing urge. Cardiac issue created by holding urges of semen, belching, thrust, tear, exertional dyspnoea. Headache is caused by holding urges of urine, stool, sneezing, sleep.

Suppressible mental urges are greed, sadness, fear, anger, ego, jealous, shamelessness, excess attachment.

Suppressible natural urges are excess talk, excess harsh talk, backbiting use of false words and irrelevant talk.

Suppressible physical urges are actions which harm others like stealing, cheating, violence and extra marital affair.

There are proper seasonal guidelines for diet and lifestyle in 6 different seasons which one should follow and avoid. These seasons are *Varsha Ritu* (rainy season), *Sharad Ritu* (autumn season), *Hemant Ritu* (winter season), *Shishir Ritu* (Excess winter season), *Basant Ritu* (spring season), *Grism Ritu* (summer season).

For example, in *Hemant* and *Shishir Ritu* (winter season) digestive fire is good, so one can take *Guru* substances (heavy to digest) and should avoid cold and light substances. One should wear woollen cloth and live in house where proper heating arrangement is present.

In *Vasant Ritu* (spring season) one should not take heavy, cold, oily and sweet substances and also do not sleep in day time, otherwise *Kapha Doshas* will increase and it lower down the digestive fire and *Kaphaj* disease will aggravate. Do exercise, take honey and drink ginger water in this season.

In *Grism Ritu* (summer season) don't take sour, salty and spicy food item and avoid alcohol. Don't do sex and exercise too.

In *Varsha Ritu* (Rainy season) avoid day sleeping, excess coitus, exercise, bare foot travelling and sun bath. Use honey water and boiled water in drinking. Take only light food in this season.

In *Sharad Ritu* (Autumn season) avoid curd intake, sun light, oil, spicy beverages, day time sleeping and excess food. Take light diet.

Seasonal detoxification (*Panchakarma*) is advised in 3 seasons. For example *Basti* procedure is advised for avoidance of *Vaataj* disease in rainy season. *Virechan* procedure (purgation) is

Advised in autumn season to avoid *Pittaj* disease. *Vaman* procedure (vomiting) is advised in spring season to avoid *Kaphaj* disease.

By these procedures body becomes toxin free and good health can enjoy by individual.

There is also a special concept of *Ritu Sandhi* in *Ayurveda* to live healthy life. In this, specific precaution taken by an individual during 14 days of seasonal changes in which 7days from previous *Ritu* and next 7 days from coming *Ritu*. In it gradually leaving previous diet and lifestyle and accepting coming *Ritu* diet and lifestyle.

Another most important constituent of healthy life is Yoga. Yoga includes *Yama*, *Niyama*, *Aasana*. *Pranayam*, *Pratyahar*, *Dharana*, *Dhyan* and *Samadhi* also known as *Astang* Yoga.

Yama and *Niyam* are rules and regulation which one should follow to get maximum result of *Aasanas* and *Pranayam*.

By *Aasanas* and *Pranayam* proper blood circulation is achieved in body which is essential for healthy life. During any *Aasanas* mainly contraction and relaxation of muscles takes place by which blood flow changes and body parts becomes strengthen. By *Pranayama* proper inhalation and exhalation occur. By this process maximum oxygen is reached to each and every cell of body and carbon di oxide is removed from all cells of body. By this process all channels is free from toxin so this is also known as *Naadi Shodhan Pranayam*.

There is complete range of *Aasanas* for each kind of individual whether child, student, young and old people, sitting or standing job person, healthy or diseased person. Always do Yoga in proper guidance and supervision of a Yoga trainer so that no mishappening occur.

Now will discuss about cure of diseases or treatment part i.e. how to get rid of diseases. In *Ayurveda* unique concept is of *Nidan Parivarjan* (removal of cause) for cure of any disease. It is first and for most important step towards any treatment protocol. Second step of Ayurvedic treatment is *Deepan- Pachana* and *Anuloman*. In its first digestive fire is increased or corrected for extinguishment of toxins in body and proper digestion establishment by *Deepana- Pachana* drugs and toxic material is removed from body by herbal laxatives. Third step towards any disease treatment is use of drugs opposite of disease.

There is list of specific drugs in specific disease. For example

1. *Musta* and *Parpataka* – Fever
2. *Laaja* – Vomiting
3. *Shilajeeta* - Urinary disease
4. *Amla* and *Turmeric* - *Prameha*
5. Iron- *Pandu*
6. *Vaat- Kapha- Haritaki*
7. *Pippali* – Spleen disorder
8. *Shirisha* – Poisons

9. *Guggulu*- Obesity and *Vaataja* issues
10. *Vaasa* – *Raktapitta*
11. *Kutaja* - *Atissara* (loose motion)
12. *Bhallataka* - Piles
13. *Rasanjana* - Obesity
14. *Vidanga* – Worms
15. *Triphala* – Eye diseases
16. *Guduchi* - *Vaatarakta*
17. *Takra* (Butter milk) - *Grahani*
18. *Shilajeeta* – All diseases
19. Old ghee - *Unmaada* (Mania)
20. *Madya* (alcohol) - Sadness
21. *Brahmi* - *Apasmaara* (epilepsy)
22. Milk- Insomnia
23. Thinness - Meat
24. Garlic - *Vaataja* disorder
25. Stiffness - Fomentation
26. Ascites – Camel urine and milk
27. *Nasya* - *Shirorog* (diseases of head region)
28. Acute Abscess - Blood letting
29. *Nasya* and *Kavala* (Gargling) - Mouth diseases
30. *Nasya*, *Anjana* (Medicated *Kajal*), *Tarpan* - Eye diseases
31. Milk and ghee - Old age
32. Cold water, fresh air - Fainting
33. Ginger - Low digestive fire
34. *Sura* (alcohol), bathing – Lethargies
35. Exercise - strengthen the body
36. *Khadira Saara* - *Kushtha* (skin diseases)

After cure of disease, use some herbs which maintain the power and rejuvenate body. For this special segment there are *Rasayan* and *Vajikaran* herbs are recommended. There are disease wise and body parts wise *Rasayan* herbs in classics.

For example

- * *Brahma Rasayana* - use in lethargy, greying and falling of hair, improve intelligence
- * *Haritkyadi Rasayana* - 100-year life span achievement with memory, intelligence, body strength
- * *Aamalaki Rasayana* – 1000-year life span achievement with intelligence and power
- * *Chyawanaprasha* – cure cough and cold, breathing issues, fever, heart disease, gout, problems associated with urine and semen, useful for children, old people, lean and thin persons etc
- * *Triphala Rasayana* - cure all diseases and improve intelligence, memory and life span
- * *Chitraka Rasayana* - cures piles and skin diseases
- * Before *Rasayana* intake, body should be purified so it can take maximum benefit from it.
- * *Vaajikarana Aushadhi* (drug) not only improve male power but it also improves complete immunity.

Vichaara (Thought Process) - It is for most important factor for health of an individual. Psychosomatic and Autoimmune diseases occur due to conflict in mind. *Ayurveda* focus on *Sadvritta* (good Conducts) which

should be followed by body, mind and soul. Whatever a person appears from outside it should be from inside too. Nowadays majority diseases are psychosomatic in nature due to not proper following of *Sadvritta*. Autoimmune diseases are also increasing due to not proper coordination between heart and brain. When heart and brain think in different directions then body becomes confused and body parts oppose to each other so causing incurable diseases.

Ayurveda can cure these diseases by *Aachara Rasayana* and *Sadvritta*. These are -

Always speaking truth, don't do anger, be kind to every creature of world, giving donations, don't take maximum part of bread, always think others before himself, keep neatness and cleanliness at each and every label on body, mind and soul.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The matter is collected from following

Charaka Samhita

Sushruta Samhita

Astang Sangrah

Astang Hriday

Other Ayurvedic literature and different online platform

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

By following proper Ayurvedic Diet and lifestyle (*Aahaara*, *Vihaara* and *Vichaara*) person attain and enjoy good health. By taking Ayurvedic treatment a person becomes free from disease by its roots and by following proper diet and lifestyle and leaving cause (*Nidan Parivarjan*).

Ayurveda is the only science or Pathy which can provide good health, maintain good health and harmony to the society and individual too because it focusses on all creatures of world. It is the only holistic science which give or provide all solutions for each and every individual. *Ayurveda* is pocket friendly (modern surgeries cost in lacs) and have no or minimal side effect.

So, *Ayurveda* or *Ayush* system have full scope for public health.

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